

ROLE OF STRUCTURE IN MODERN ARCHITECTURE

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Annotation: This article deals with important features of structure in modern architecture. Moreover, historical view of architecture were discussed.

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During the last two decades the history of modern architecture has been one of sorting out, developing, and transforming possibilities implicit at the beginning. What has changed more than architectural practice is the way we see buildings and talk about them. Underlying the change is the feeling, widespread but by no means universal, that the modern movement in architecture as understood by its pioneers is now over. That change in attitude describes a hope (or a fear) rather than a fact, and it also focuses attention on the nature of modernism. It is unlikely that anyone can offer a definition of modern architecture to which there are no exceptions. But at the beginning of the modern movement one commitment emerged preeminent. Modern architecture, like engineering, ought to deal only with the truths of structure and function. It wanted all architectural pleasures to derive from the straightforward encounter with necessity. Architectural fictions, the play of unnecessary forms with which the historic styles sought to transcend necessity, were rejected as unworthy. That at least describes an essential characteristic of what came to be called the International Style, to which the most important exception was Expressionism in its various national modes—the loser, for a time, in the wars of persuasion.

The final form which is adopted for a work of architecture is influenced by many factors ranging from the ideological to the severely practical. This book is concerned principally with the building as a physical object and, in particular, with the question of the structural support which must be provided for a building in order that it can maintain its shape and integrity in the physical world. The role of the building as an aesthetic object, often imbued with symbolic meaning, is, however, also central to the argument of the book; one strand of this argument considers that the contribution of the structure to the achievement of higher architectural objectives is always crucial. Technical issues are accordingly considered here within a wider agenda which encompasses considerations other than those of practicality. The relationship between the structural and the non-structural parts of a building may vary widely. In some buildings the space-enclosing elements - the walls, floors and roof - are also structural elements, capable of resisting and conducting load. In others, such as buildings with large areas of glazing on the exterior walls, the structure can be entirely separate from the space-enclosing elements .

In all cases the structure forms the basic carcass of the building - the armature to which all non-structural elements are attached. The visual treatment of structure can be subject to much variation. The structural system of a building can be given great prominence and be made to form an important part of the architectural vocabulary . At the other extreme, its presence can be visually played down with the structural elements contributing little to the appearance of the building. Between these extremes lies an infinite variety of possibilities . In all cases, however, the structure, by virtue of the significant volume which it occupies in a building, affects its visual character to some extent and it does so even if it is not directly visible. No matter how the structure is treated visually, however, the need for technical requirements to be satisfied must always be acknowledged. Structural constraints therefore exert a significant influence, overt

or hidden, on the final planning of buildings. This book is concerned with the programmatic aspects of the relationship between architecture and structure. Chapter 2, in particular, deals with the process by which the form and general arrangement of structures for buildings are determined - with the design of architectural structures, in other words. Information on basic forms of structure - the range of structural possibilities - is essential to the success of this process; this is provided in subsequent chapters which deal separately with the four principal structural materials of steel, reinforced concrete, masonry and timber.

The principal forms of loading to which buildings are subjected are gravitational loads, wind pressure loads and inertial loads caused by seismic activity. Gravitational loads, which are caused by the weight of the building itself and of its contents, act vertically downwards; wind and seismic loads have significant horizontal components but can also act vertically. To perform satisfactorily a structure must be capable of achieving a stable state of static equilibrium in response to all of these loads - to load from any direction, in other words. This is the primary requirement; the form and general arrangement of a structure must be such as to make this possible. The distinction between the requirements for stability and equilibrium is an important one and the basic principles are illustrated in Fig. 1.5. Equilibrium occurs when the reactions at the foundations of a structure exactly balance and counteract the applied load; if it were not in equilibrium the structure would change its position in response to the load. Stability is concerned with the ability of a structural arrangement which is in equilibrium to accommodate small disturbances without suffering a major change of shape. The first of the beam/column frameworks. Most architectural structures are of the postand-beam type and consist of horizontal spanning elements supported on vertical columns or walls. A characteristic of this type of structure is that the horizontal elements are subjected to bending-type internal forces under the action of gravitational load (normally the primary load on an architectural

structure). This has two consequences. Firstly, it requires that the structural material be capable of resisting both tension and compression (e.g. steel, reinforced concrete, timber). Secondly, it is an inefficient type of structure (larger volumes of material are required to support a given load than are necessary with other types of structure).¹ The post-and-beam structure has the great advantage that it is simple and therefore cheap to construct. This group of structures can be subdivided into the two categories of 'skeleton-frame' structures and 'panel' structures. The latter are also loadbearing-wall structures. Skeleton-frame structures consist of a network of beams and columns which support floor slabs and roof cladding and to which wall cladding is attached. The configuration of the beam-and-column grid which is adopted in a particular case depends on the overall form of the building concerned, on the internal planning requirements and on the properties of the particular structural material which has been chosen - see Chapters 3 to 6. In this type of arrangement the structure occupies a relatively small volume and this is in fact one of its principal advantages. Considerable freedom is available to the building designer in the matter of internal planning because both the internal partition walls and the exterior walls are non-loadbearing. Large wall-free spaces can therefore be created in the interiors and different plan-forms adopted at different levels in multi-storey buildings. The choice of external treatment is wide. Relatively fragile materials such as glass can be used and little restriction is placed on the locations of doors and windows

To sum up, the architect who considers him or herself to be an artist, dealing through the medium of built form with the philosophical preoccupations of the age in which he or she lives, is surely engaged in a titanic struggle. One aspect of that struggle is the need to determine building forms which are structurally viable. All artists must acquire mastery of the technology of their chosen medium but few face difficulties which are as formidable as those who choose buildings as their means of expression. The sculptor has to contend with

similar structural problems but his or her difficulties are trivial by comparison with those of the architect. The difference is one of scale - the size of a building, compared to that of a work of sculpture, means that the technical hurdle which must be surmounted by the architect is of a different order of magnitude to those which are faced by most other artists

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